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“DIODES ARE VITAL IN ELECTRONICS”

Technological developments are moving forward every day through research and innovations looking at solutions for every problem and improving production, making life better for humankind. Among other technologies, electronics plays a vital role in the technological advancement embedded in every innovation chain, especially in control processes. Electronic devices are fabricated by integrating several basic components that serve as circuit elements that work together to perform tasks. Among these components is a diode, a tiny component that plays a very important role in every electronic system, from simple circuits to advanced computer systems. Only the people working behind electronics (e.g., engineers, technicians, students, and related fields) know everything about the capability of this diode, without this tiny device electronics system cannot work.

In the world today, people should start realizing and appreciating the countless contributions of diodes. This simple but important component in electronics is made of two semiconductor junctions: the P-type is a positive charge carrier, and the N-type is a negative charge carrier, wherein the diode strictly follows the electric charge polarity. When a diode receives a correct polarity of electric charge, it is called a forward bias, allowing current flow, whereas if the diode receives an opposite charge, it is called a reverse bias, which prohibits current flow. That is why, in principle, the diode is defined as a basic electronic component that allows electrons to flow in only one direction.

Several types of diodes have been specially designed for use in electronic systems according to their purpose. Two common types of diodes perform basic functions, but they are very important for every system: rectifier diodes, which are used to convert alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC) in power supplies; light-emitting diodes (LED), which are used to emit light for visual signal indicators; and video displays such as those used in LED wall displays. Other diodes are designed for signal processing, such as signal oscillation, high-frequency switch protection, and radio-frequency tuning.

With the special function of this component, many power supply types are realized and created for every purpose, from a linear-type power supply to a switch mode power supply (SMPS), which are both important. Another important function of this small component is in the signal lines to prevent crosstalk, protect against interference, and prevent unwanted frequencies. In computer systems, diodes are arranged to perform logical operations.

An electronics student learns diodes in the classroom to understand the theory and experience hands-on project exercises in the laboratory on how diodes convert alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC) in a

power supply using equipment such as voltmeters and oscilloscopes for visual observations. DC circuit applications of diodes were observed by students as to how these tiny components were used to perform logical functions in computation circuits where the diode blocks the DC signal flow in reverse current mode and allows the DC signal to flow in forward current mode.

The contribution of diodes to electronics is remarkable and has a strong impact on technological advancement, addressing innovation problems by utilizing electronic circuits, particularly in control systems that are crucial in every process, making every process automated, and making our daily life easy and comfortable by using electronic devices such as smartphones, advanced household appliances, personal computers, and industrial equipment. This is why diodes are vital in electronics.

